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Instructional Strategies Utilized in Teaching Radar-Related Courses

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Introduction

Education is a lifelong process. It is the backbone for individual success and the appreciation of one's life history. It is the foundation for upgrading an individual's knowledge and skills to the highest levels. In line with this, military personnel are considered adult learners, as they are already performing their mandated tasks in securing the peace and sovereignty of the people and the country at a relatively young age, with diverse learning needs. Therefore, it is believed that pursuing Education and a broader spectrum of knowledge is paramount for an adult learner, specifically a soldier, whether they have already completed a four-year degree course or not. It is said that Learning is a continuous process. No matter how diverse people are in terms of learning, their age, job, and affiliations, learning will always be present because upgrading of skills and knowledge is always ongoing through training and schooling in a particular institution. Most especially to adult learners, they tend to learn best through real-life experiences, problems, life and death situations on the ground, aerial, and naval troops, where in it develop their critical thinking abilities, confidence in doing their job, vigilance, alertness, and quick decision-making skills, which is very crucial, relevant and timely in the lives of military personnel.

To design and develop policies and programs that respond to adult learners' needs, it is essential to understand the dynamics that underlie adults' participation and non-participation in learning. If not fully captured, policies and programs are not able to engage those adults who need learning the most. Evaluations and studies on adult learning policies consistently report that specifically disadvantaged adult learners can hardly be re-engaged in learning, despite tailoring the approach to solving group-specific barriers. Adult learning policies need to be based on an understanding of the inequalities in the uptake and benefits of learning, and why adults might not participate. This needs to go beyond a mere insight into barriers that, once removed, no longer provide a reason for adults not to participate. This article aims to delve deeper into understanding what makes adults choose to learn. (Borek et al., 2023).

With this theory in mind, since adult learners are diverse learners, to design and develop effective strategies or programs of instruction, there is a need to understand the adult learners' needs and to delve deeper into what makes adults choose to learn. For instance, in the military organization, the instructors already understood that military personnel assigned to different Units have their mission or goals to support the country, whereas in the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station, performing excellent radar operations and capabilities is the priority and the salient goals to achieve our mission. Since the need to learn radar operations was already identified, crafting or applying the instructional strategies or the learning approaches starts at this point. Instructors are responsible for ensuring that the students attending radar-related courses learn the necessary skills and knowledge to operate the radars manually. It always starts with proper learning motivation. That is why the instructors must conduct or incorporate feedback mechanisms to know and identify different problems of the students concerning radar-related courses or their strategies as a way of innovation and improvement, which later on results in better learning among military personnel.

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The 580th Aircraft Control and Wing is best known as the Eyes and Ears of the Philippine Air Force and the Home of the Air Battle Managers for its air defense capabilities and as the only radar Unit that provides radar-related schooling to active military personnel in the Philippine Air Force. At present, the Wing has five (5) Radar sites situated throughout the islands of Luzon and Mindanao that cover the Philippine Air Defense Identification Zone (PADIZ). All five Radar Sites are a significant part of the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station, City of San Fernando, La Union. To man these radar sites, military personnel who are deployed must possess Radar-Related schooling to continue its prowess, activation and help achieve the Wing's Vision and Mission in carrying and supporting the Air Defense Mission which becomes the role of the instructors to produce excellent Radar Operators, Radar Maintenance, Air Weapons Controllers and even Air Battle Managers utilizing their instructional strategies in teaching Radar-related courses to active military personnel. The Philippines possesses different training schools throughout Luzon, Visayas and Mindanao that provides academics and practical exercises to all its uniformed personnel such as the Armed forces of the Philippines.

Instructors are responsible for providing a premium in core competencies in planning and implementing classroom instruction, and possess the necessary knowledge of the standards set forth for personnel to be ready for radar operations, air weapons controller, radar maintenance, air surveillance, and Air Battle Management. The skills and attitude of each personnel member needed to be enhanced and standardized, as they are the future of the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, which will fulfill the roles of radar operators, maintenance personnel, surveillance controllers, and air battle managers with the help of instructors teaching radar courses to the personnel. Air Defense is the first line of defense in detecting unknown tracks and intrusions from other aircraft without proper authority to enter the Philippine Area of Responsibility, so knowing that Wallace Air Station produces excellent students with great performances on Radar operations and maintenance is of utmost importance since radar operations is crucial when it comes to safeguarding, scanning the skies all day and night and guiding friendly planes on their flight to successfully carry out their mission and tasks.

This study served as a support for military personnel (officers and enlisted) who are willing to pursue their civilian education as their learning tool in making a Research proposal. This study served as the light to all the Aircraft Controller Instructors of the 580th ACWW on how they deliver and promote better education to all Active Military personnel (Officers and Enlisted) in 580th ACWW. Additionally, for Educational Institutions, this study served as a guide and support in learning different teaching strategies from the Instructors in a Military Perspective, in which greatly helped those who desired to learn more about military education. Lastly, this study was essential not only to those students who are doing their research proposal which is related with military education/training or schooling but for the Researcher as well, where in it honed her skills and knowledge in terms of writing a research paper, helped her feel motivated, dedicated and fulfilled as Military Enlisted personnel who kept on pursuing higher education (Civilian Schooling).

The study answered the research questions that pertains to: (1) What is the extent of practice of the instructional strategies Instructors used in teaching radar-related courses based on the experiences of the respondents; (2); Is there a significant difference on the extent of practice of the different instructional strategies along academic phase and synthetic phase; and (3) What output can be proposed to promote better learning among active military personnel who undergo radar-related courses?

Theoretical Framework

Theories or Concepts that are found essential to the study are the Adult Learning Theory, Cognitive Load Theory, Experiential Learning Theory, Military Pedagogy, Transformative Learning Theory, and

Social Learning Theory. Adult Learning Theory is based on an American educator, well known for the use of the term Andragogy as synonymous with adult education. According to Knowles (1997), andragogy is the art and science of [adult learning](#). Additionally, according to Malcolm Knowles, Andragogy Theory is Similar to the term pedagogy, which addresses the method of teaching in children, while andragogy examines the process by which adults learn. It was initially focused on adults; the term andragogy has broadened to include any educational practice with a student-driven approach. Andragogy is a relatively new concept that was created less than 200 years ago. Many professionals, including educators and philosophers, have debated whether there is a difference between pedagogy and andragogy (Kurt, 2020).

This theory is relevant to the study since the respondents are adult learners who are military personnel assigned to Wallace Air Station. It is quite evident that adult learners are very particular when it comes to learning. They are very interested in topics associated with different real-life experiences, which are significant to their job or personal life. They learn best when a problem arises. They tend to look for immediate answers to come up with a solution to a certain adversity. Especially in the military organization, personnel look for quick ways to come up with better solutions to a problem that comes their way. They prefer everything with quicker than expected. Just like in Wallace Air Station, since this is the only radar station that provides radar-related schooling in the whole Philippine Air Force Organization, they made sure that every personnel may it be officers and enlisted personnel who are newly assigned Airman and Airwoman to undergo immediate radar-related schooling to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in performing radar operations, radar maintenance, air surveillance, air battle management, aircraft control and command and control in support to the Wing's mission and vision in providing radar capabilities to the Philippine area of responsibility to protect our sovereignty.

Additionally, since military personnel are adult learners, they understand the learning needs and capacities of adults by aligning with their life goals, changing workplace, and societal needs. They also tend to acquire self-directed learning that demonstrates a preference for autonomy in the process of their learning objectives, methods, use of resources, and conducting self-assessments of their progress. Subject personnel learn best through life experiences, eagerness to learn, and intrinsic motivation to further enhance their knowledge and skills in performing actual radar operations. However, there are challenges to be undertaken as well such as time constraints, confidence issues, financial considerations and self-doubt, but through corroboration with other students attending radar-related courses, quality teaching through the use of effective instructional materials by qualified instructors, I believe that these adult learners will do their best especially in performing their job manually in a real-world scenario as expected from personnel assigned in a radar station.

The second one is the Cognitive Load Theory, which is an instructional theory based on our knowledge of [human cognition](#) (Sweller et al., 2011). Since its inception in the 1980s (e.g., Sweller, 1988), the theory has used aspects of human cognitive architecture to generate experimental, instructional effects. These effects are demonstrated when novel instructional procedures are compared with more traditional procedures as part of a randomized, controlled experiment.

This theory is of great relevance to the study since it uses aspects of human cognition to generate experimental, instructional effects among human beings. As part of the human race, we have this so cold human cognitive abilities and skills, which make us a more reliable source of information, able to explain further about certain topics that no other living being can. Through the use of cognitive load theory, humans can know the difference between present and past experiences. This becomes the architect for better and enhanced learning. This helps explain how the brain processes the information and learn at the end of the day, which makes this theory relevant in the everyday lives of military personnel.

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Thirdly is the experiential Learning theory, which is proposed by Kolb (2022). It takes a more holistic approach and emphasizes how experiences, including cognition, environmental factors, and emotions, influence the learning process. This type of learning can be defined as "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming the experience." In Wallace Air Station, they use the strategy called Experiential learning, where personnel tend to learn by doing the job in a real scenario. Military personnel can distinguish what they have to and do not have to do in their job, such as radar operations. This theory is of great significance to the study since military personnel tend to learn best through their experiences, may it be in the environment, the way they process things in their minds, or even personal emotions that influence the learning process. Just like how the saying goes, "Learning by Doing", one can never achieve greatness without experiencing what they want to achieve in life. Once you realize what you need to do as a person who wants to learn, you have to accomplish and experience everything first before learning, and become a master of development.

The fourth theory is the Military Pedagogy, as mentioned in the study of Juhary (2015), according to Toiskallio, (2003), comes under "military sciences that look into the philosophies, conceptions, visions, doctrines, aims, approaches and technologies of military education and training". Scholars argued that the role of military pedagogy will increase due to the demands of higher education opportunities for military personnel. The involvement of these personnel in military and humanitarian operations calls for systematic education and training (Juhary, 2015). According to Hartman (2022), Humboldt emphasized in his writing on defending the nation through three main components: The formation of soldiers' personality, the efficiency of pedagogy within the military organizations, and the political and social development of civil society. These theories and concepts play a vital role in the utilization of Instructional Strategies/methods when teaching students

This theory is of utmost importance to the study because as an educator/Instructor it is important to help students learn using different kinds of learning strategies particularly in teaching older students and those who already possesses job stability just like personnel in the Armed Forces of the Philippines/Military for them to be able to grasp new ideas and concepts regarding on their present jobs and as to how they can perform and contribute well in the organization. It is also based on the notion and research that learning can be gained from different long-term experiences, depending on the instructors how they will be able to transform these experiences into an effective approach and instructional procedure in teaching their students. As an Instructional Leader, you can also create and develop different instructional materials conducive to learning that can also be done or given during the assessment and evaluation phase in the teaching-learning process. Since the study focuses more on the education and courses being taught in a military organization, Instructors may also utilize the already published, distributed manuals about Doctrines and philosophies, conceptions, visions, aims/mission, approaches, and technologies being utilized as part of the traditions, culture, and norms in the military organization.

Fifthly, the Transformative learning theory of Mezirow (2020). It is a theory of learning that particularly focuses on adult education and young adult learning. Transformative learning, sometimes called transformational learning, focuses on the idea that learners can adjust their thinking based on new information. Mezirow's initial research led him to theorize that adults don't apply their old understanding to new situations; instead, they find they need to look at new perspectives to get a new understanding of things as they change.

This theory is equally significant to the study because nothing is constant in this world except change. Humans and even technologies are bound to change as time goes by. This is where transformative learning theory occurs. It focuses on learning transformation. From a military perspective, we tend to find ways to adapt; our old understanding cannot be applied to new

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situations because it needs new perspectives to get a new understanding of things as they change, which leads to learning opportunities among learners and teachers alike. Just like in the strategies being utilized by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses, there's a need to constantly check and revise their doctrines, mandates, and standard operating procedures in developing a program of instructions for better teaching-learning to take place. Perhaps, what they have written previously would not be as necessary as of the moment since old understanding of things cannot be the solution to today's adversities. There is a must for transformative learning that associates with the current problems, trends, global and economic opportunities, and possibilities that would aid the learning needs of the students nowadays in a military training school.

Lastly is the Social Learning Theory: Cognitive and Behavioral Approaches, where Social learning theory (SLT) and social cognitive theory (SCT) identify learning as a dynamic interaction between people, environment, and behavior. Engagement in a social context involves a dual process of making meaning. This study focuses on the concepts of SLT and SCL theorized by Albert Bandura, complemented by other relevant literature (Firnansyah et al., 2022). This Theory is relevant to the study, since the participants of this study are adult learners, particularly military personnel assigned to Wallace Air Station, undergoing radar-related schooling. One of the instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses was Collaborative Learning, and determined as very highly effective, meaning that collaboration with other students, teacher-student interaction, and learning itself a social process.

To ensure learning among adult learners, there is a need for proper collaboration with other people present in that area, which is the classroom or other learning facilities. Social interaction between people, environment, and behaviour is paramount in the everyday life of the 580ACWW personnel. They need to speak up their minds, relate with other people, develop social skills, interaction skills, and collaboration skills since this is necessary in performing radar operations, air surveillance, aircraft control, radar maintenance and air battle management during tracking, and fighting other aircraft in an interception scenario when an enemy aircraft or unauthorized aircraft has crossed the Philippine Area of responsibility. This ensures alignment of goals, military standards, confidence among the learners, and the production of quality performance. These theories primarily guide the design and implementation of radar training strategies, ensuring structured learning while allowing for flexibility in adapting to real-world defense scenarios.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the Conceptual Framework of the study. It discusses the Input, Process, and Output of the study. This study's conceptual framework is grounded in the Input-Process-Output model, which provides a clear roadmap for improving the teaching of radar-related courses for military personnel. The input phase encompasses a diverse range of instructional strategies that instructors currently employ, including direct instruction, collaborative learning, technology integration, experiential learning, practical exercises, field studies, research activities, assessment methods, and on-the-job training (OJT). These inputs represent the foundational teaching approaches and learning experiences designed to build both theoretical knowledge and practical skills necessary for effective radar operation. By capturing this broad spectrum of strategies, the study acknowledges the complex and multifaceted nature of military technical education, emphasizing how varied approaches contribute to learner engagement and competence.

The process phase involves a thorough analysis of how these instructional strategies impact learning outcomes. This includes collecting and evaluating data on the effectiveness of each method based on the experiences and feedback of graduates. Through this analytical lens, the study identifies strengths, gaps, and opportunities for enhancement, paying special attention to how learners apply

their knowledge in real-world radar operations. Ultimately, the output of this process is a carefully crafted instructional enhancement plan or training module, designed to refine and optimize teaching practices based on evidence. These outputs are intended to provide practical, actionable guidance for instructors to deliver more effective, engaging, and relevant radar training, ensuring that students are better prepared for their critical roles. This cyclical framework thus supports continuous improvement by linking current instructional realities with informed strategies for future teaching excellence.

Figure 1. Integrated Learning Strategies in Radar Operations

Review of Literature

Instructional Strategies in the Military Context

Instructional design (ID) is one of the many strategies that are being utilized in teaching, most especially in the Military Organization. Instructional design is the systematic process by which education and training programs are designed, developed, and delivered consistently and reliably. The terms instructional design (ID), instructional technology, educational technology, curriculum design, and instructional systems design (ISD), are often used interchangeably. The outcome of this instruction may be directly observable and scientifically measured or completely hidden and assumed. There are many instructional design models, but many are based on the [ADDIE model](#) with the five phases: analysis, design, development, [implementation](#), and [evaluation](#) (Basu, 2021).

This design is significant to the study because different instructional strategies are being utilized in teaching learners. They differ from one another, physically, mentally, emotionally, and even in the learning process. They possess different learning styles, and as an educator, one must comprehend and adapt to be able to deliver quality and clear learning to the students. Whatever strategies a teacher uses, they must be consistent, reliable, and effective for an engaging and inspiring teaching-learning process to take place. In Wallace Air Station, instructors utilized different instructional strategies to cater to the learning needs of the students undergoing radar-related courses because they want to make sure that they produce excellent radar operators, surveillance, radar maintenance, and air battle managers. This is paramount since the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing is responsible for detecting unknown intrusions of aircraft within the Philippine area of responsibility and other aerial threats that can cause harm in the country and its citizens.

There are studies conducted internationally regarding strategies utilized while teaching in the Military. One of which is entitled "Problem-Based Strategies for Teaching military English (Niculescu, 2019) from the Foreign Language Centre of the Land Forces Headquarters, Sibiu, Romania. Her study identified a strategy called Problem-Based Learning (PBL), which is based on complex real-life problems, aiming to motivate, focus, and initiate student learning. This approach facilitates students' cooperation and, in the long run, empowers recipients to actively pursue and engage in their learning. Integrated in the framework of Bloom's model of cognitive levels, well-constructed PBL problems stimulate learners to function at high levels of analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

In a military organization, they are faced with new and different challenges in their everyday lives, especially since their job is to continue promoting peace, aiding the nation with aerial support against outside threats. Radar Operations are very crucial and timely in the Philippine Area of Responsibility. Operators and air battle managers conduct air surveillance activities to detect known and unknown tracks in the airspace within the Philippine Air Defense Identification Zone. Whenever unknown aircraft cross the PADIZ point, radar operators and air battle managers conduct challenges to identify the unknown aircraft, whether it's an enemy aircraft or not. They conduct air surveillance 24/7, so military personnel assigned to radar stations must be equipped with knowledge and skills to perform these activities in support of the mission of the Air Defense Command, Philippine Air Force, to bring aid to our nation. Through PBL, learners acquire necessary skills such as being vigilant, confidence in solving problems, confidence in performing their designated tasks, knowing they do their best in every job assigned to them, and it hones their critical thinking abilities, which is very significant in challenging unknown tracks in the Philippine Air Space.

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A similar study was also done locally here in the Philippines and was created by personnel in the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP), particularly in the Philippine Army, which is entitled the PA ET&D Strategic Plan (Sagario, 2022). This approach was formulated as a way to support the strategic objectives of the Army Transformation Roadmap (ATR) to 2040, one of which is to ensure responsive doctrine development and a complementary training system.

This strategy of the Philippine Army is very similar to the different mandates, policies, and standing operating procedures of the Philippine Air Force. The PAF crafted a transformation Road map, which is entitled Flight Plan 2040 Road Map, since the PAF is focused on aerial defense. This Flight Plan 2040 includes different visions and missions to be conducted throughout the years until 2040. This plan is constantly undergoing changes, revisions, and updates throughout the years to continuously keep the aerial battle plans updated to be used as necessary. In Wallace Air Station, the Officers and Enlisted Personnel alike brainstorm, conducting meetings and crafting of different SOPs quarterly with regards to the improvement of the air battle plan and management depending on how the world advances, global trends and other necessary information to promote excellence in the field of radar operations in support the mission of the Air Defense Command and the whole Philippine Air Force.

Another theory regarding instructional strategies in the military field is the Instructional Strategies Framework for military training systems. Modern homeland and coalition forces operate in a variety of complex, stressful, and ambiguous environments (Laurence, 2012; Salas et al., 2006). These situations require the ability to adapt to novel situations, make difficult decisions, and solve complex problems in both war-fighting and peacekeeping scenarios (Andrews et al., 2010; Merrenboer, 2007). To date, training for these environments has best been accomplished using technology-based experiential learning approaches (Raybourn, 2007). The rationale for such approaches is that computer-based training, including virtual-reality simulation, offers safe, efficient, and effective training that has practical and economical advantages over more traditional methods. Consequently, the United States military has increasingly invested in the development of replicable and generalizable training systems (Salas et al., 2006).

As mentioned previously, solving complex problems, especially in dealing with stressful and ambiguous environments such as in war-fighting scenarios, military personnel must be ready and vigilant in terms of solving these problems on their own. They must be thorough, quick thinker, and precise in dealing with their enemies. We also learn from our experiences; we need to use these experiences to excel in the field, and we will not take a different turn of events that will cost our precious lives. Training in a real-life scenario is efficient in delivering effective lessons among the students because they learn by doing it. Just like in the military, before becoming one, you have to experience the training first to learn the things you need to do to become a real soldier, especially in a real McCoy situation.

The goal of this review is to address this problem by creating an organized framework for the selection of research-based instructional strategies relevant to the military. Specifically, the grounded-theory approach (Wolfswinkel et al., 2011) was used to characterize strategies based on the time at which the strategy is implemented within the training cycle (i.e., pre-training, during-training, post-training), the expertise level of trainees (i.e., novice, journeyman, expert), and the type of knowledge to be trained (i.e., declarative, procedural, conceptual, integrated).

This basic idea is the key component of a learner-centered approach to instructional design – basing the selection of instructional strategies on what is known about human cognition, and in particular, the role of trainees' prior knowledge in learning new material. Although this approach is well supported in the literature, military training systems are often not designed accordingly. Further, as mentioned in the study of Buhari, (2012) entitled *Constructivist Approaches are Compatible with Human Cognitive Architecture: A Response to Kirschner, Sweller, and Clark* in their argument, Kirschner

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et al., (2006) affirm that minimal guided instruction approaches are less effective and efficient than fully guided instruction approaches because they ignore the structures that constitute human cognitive architecture. Rather, such systems often employ minimally guided approaches (e.g., discovery learning, constructivist approaches, problem-based learning, experiential learning, inquiry-based).

Thus, different training environments have very different goals in terms of the types of knowledge that are to be targeted. Further, different instructional strategies are more appropriate for supporting different types of knowledge (Koedinger et al., 2012). Therefore, one of the goals of this review is to facilitate the selection of instructional strategies based on the specific type of knowledge associated with the goals of the training environment.

Another important consideration in designing adaptive instruction is the applicability of strategies primarily designed for improving academic learning to enhancing military training outcomes. Fortunately, research has suggested that cognitive instructional theories and methods more targeted toward the context of academic learning (e.g., cognitive load theory, the cognitive theory of multimedia learning, and expertise development) can be applied toward enhancing military training (Vogel-Walcutt et al., 2010, Williams et al., 2008). Recommendations included providing an advance organizer prior to training (Fiore et al., 2008), providing worked examples of problems rather than conventional problem-solving practice (e.g., Darabi et al., 2007), and providing metacognitive prompting during training (Cuevas et al., 2004). Additionally, recent studies have shown that instructional strategies originally designed for academic learning can be effectively applied to enhance military training outcomes (Fiorella et al., 2012; Fiore et al., 2008). For example, in one study by Fiorella et al. (2012), the modality principle of multimedia learning (i.e., text should be spoken rather than printed when accompanying other visuals (Mayer, 2009) was applied toward the provision of real-time feedback during simulation-based training of a military Call for Fire task.

This study would also allow us to identify the gaps in practice of the teaching strategies used in the military education locally and internationally, most specifically here in the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station, City of San Fernando, La Union, as the only Radar Station that provides Radar Courses in the whole Philippine Air Force Organization. The researcher would like to acquire the knowledge on what are the different experiences of the students graduated from previous Radar-Related courses, what specific strategies utilized by the Instructors that they learned from or gained knowledge the most, how effective these strategies are in the academic and synthetic phases for the students to be more equipped with necessary skills in radar operations and whether the students will likely to commit an error after Graduation and how does these strategies help them perform their duties well in reality when the said students who have graduated are given the task/duty to perform their already acquired knowledge and skills in operating the Radar most especially in detecting unknown intrusions in the Philippine Defense Area of operations (PDAO) without the presence of any instructors?

Instructional Strategies for Adult Learners

Different studies relate to Instructional strategies for Adult Learners. The first study, "Adult Learning: A Multifaceted Endeavor is a new Directions in Adult and Continuing Education. In offering a brief synopsis of each article and reflecting on the ways adult learning theories have evolved since the first update was published in 1993, this explains several themes that characterize that evolution: (1) the continued importance of foundational learning theories, (2) the diversity of learners and learning, and (3) the presence of technology in today's world. Since the origins of various adult learning theories, scholars have added and revised various theories based on critiques. Scholars have become

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increasingly aware of the impact of the sociocultural context and various positionalities, such as race, class, gender, and sexual orientation, on the learner and learning.

As we have learned more about adult learners and adult learning, there has been an effort to become more inclusive. We learn more about how the intersection of different positionalities affects the teaching/learning transaction. We understand that older adult learners may prefer larger fonts on printed materials (Baumgartner & Carr-Chellman, 2024).

This study focused more on how adult learners adapt to the modern world. Being inclusive and updated with the different things that were changed 30 years ago, and continuously evolving for a better and brighter future, makes life easier. According to Baumgartner & Carr-Chellman (2024), diversity of learners, learning, and the presence of technological advancements increasingly impact the perceptions of adult learners in the teaching-learning process. Just as in the military field, instructors learned how to better interact with and serve other individuals and to be inclusive. They also made changes to the mandates, policies, standard operating procedures, and rules and regulations that military personnel must follow, using these as a learning mechanism in today's modern world.

As military personnel assigned to the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, I have experienced different changes in the ways of the military organization since I enlisted in 2018. The Armed Forces of the Philippines views the different global trends as an opportunity for improvement and innovation, most especially in a Radar Unit such as the Wallace Air Station, which is responsible for providing radar capabilities in the Philippines. Military personnel are adult learners; therefore, they have learned how to be inclusive in today's generation. Being advanced, updated, and consistently adapting to changes is very important in performing the necessary functions of each personnel assigned in Wallace Air Station. This Unit is responsible for providing radar capabilities in the entire Philippine Air Force, which enables them to support the mission of the Air Defense Command as we execute excellent air surveillance capabilities, tracking, monitoring, challenging, and importantly, fighting aircraft as necessary during interceptions whenever an unauthorized aircraft has crossed into the Philippine Air Defense Identification Zone (PADIZ).

Secondly, it is a theoretical construct, the science of adult learning, as a means for understanding the needs of adult learners in higher education or workplace training, specifically when designing technology-mediated instruction, such as online courses or e-learning modules. The problem addressed with this theory is the lack of success of adults in distance education compared to traditional-aged peers; I believe this is partially attributable to instructional strategies that were designed for traditional-aged students. Based on a review of the literature on lifespan psychology and cognitive neuroscience, focusing on adult cognition in middle adulthood, I propose that there are significant differences that should be addressed in instructional design to improve the success of adult learners (Fensie, 2023).

As previously discussed, learners tend to learn differently. As time goes on, everything changes; therefore, utilization of instructional strategies must be up to date as well. In this theory, Fensie believed that significant differences should be addressed in instructional design to improve and ensure the learning success of adult learners, most especially those learners who are thriving in their field of work. As part of the 21st Century, educators must adapt and use the global trends as an opportunity for innovation and crafting of instructional strategies/design that is relevant to today's generation and advancement, to ensure the success of adult learners today. In Wallace Air Station, the Officers and senior leaders and Air Battle Managers, see to it that they continuously conduct updates and revision of the current SOPs, mandates and policies about the curriculum for the program of instruction that relates to the radar-related schooling that are being conducted in this Unit to provide graduates who are expert in Air Surveillance, Aircraft Control, Air Battle Management, maintenance and other radar functions. Being updated means efficiency in providing radar capabilities in support of the mission

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and vision of the Philippine Air Force as part of the security and sovereignty of our country, the Philippines.

Methods

Research Design

The study utilized the Quantitative research design. According to Bhandari (2023) Quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and [generalize](#) results to wider populations, which is the opposite of [qualitative research](#), which involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data (e.g., text, video, or audio). The survey questionnaire was validated and conducted reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha on those personnel who were graduates of Radar-related courses in Wallace Air Station, garnering 0.99% with a descriptive equivalent of Excellent.

To answer Research Question 2 with regard to the significant difference of the different instructional strategies used was determined through Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and was further discussed in the discussion part of the study. ANOVA is an analysis tool used in statistics that splits an observed aggregate variability found within a data set into two parts: systematic factors and random factors (Kenton, 2024).

Participants

The respondents of the study were the 53 graduates of Radar-Related courses of 580th ACWW, Wallace Air Station, City of San Fernando, La Union, from CY-2022- 2024. They were selected by using purposive sampling since they have been performing radar functions and operations in the institution for a certain period, they were also equipped with necessary skills and knowledge in radar operations, radar maintenance, aircraft control, air surveillance and air battle management, which is very crucial and timely at Wallace Air Station, and can easily explain and identify the extent of practice of Instructional Strategies/methods used by the instructors in teaching radar related courses to active military personnel (Officers and Enlisted Personnel) of 580th ACWW. The total population/respondents of the study belong to a military category composed of 12 Officers and 41 Enlisted Personnel, a total of 53 graduates of different Radar Courses from CY-2022-2024 who have rendered at least five years in the service/institution and have been assigned to 580th ACWW, Wallace Air Station, CSFLU for that period.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the 53 respondents. The respondents' profiles considered in this study included the number of years in service and Military Category (Officer and Enlisted Personnel). Frequency count and percentage were used as statistical tools in the description of the respondent's profile.

The data indicated that most respondents, who comprised 49.06%, had 6-8 years in the service, followed by those personnel over 9-15 years in service at 26.42%. The third in rank was those personnel within 5 years in the service at 16.98%, followed by the least, which belongs to those over 16 years and above in the service at 7.55%. As to the military category (Officer and EP), the majority of respondents are Enlisted Personnel, accounting for 77.36%, followed by Officers with 22.64%.

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	%
No. of years in Service	5 years	9	16.98%
	6-8 years	26	49.06%

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		9-15 years	14	26.42%
		16 years and above	4	7.55%
Military	Personnel	Officer	12	22.64%
Category		Enlisted Personnel	41	77.36%

The study was conducted in the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station, City of San Fernando, La Union, with a total population of 588 Military personnel, with 101 Officers and 487 Enlisted Personnel assigned. The researcher chose the locale to find out the Extent of Practice of the Instructional Strategies utilized by the Instructors in teaching radar related courses based on the experiences of the military students who have already graduated from radar courses since 580th ACWW is the only Radar Unit here in the Philippines that provides Radar Schooling/Courses as part of the Philippine Air Force Organization that serve as a support to those other personnel who wants to pursue higher education as their guide in writing their Thesis Proposal related to Education.

Data Measures

A researcher made a survey questionnaire to determine the extent of practice of the instructional strategies used by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses based on the experiences of graduates of radar courses (See Appendix D). The questionnaire included indicators for instructional strategies. It used a 5-point Likert Scale with the following qualitative descriptions: 5-Always Practiced; 4-Often Practiced; 3-Sometimes Practiced; 2-Rarely Practiced, and 1-Never Practiced.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure was based on the research questions of the study. These were the steps on how the data was gathered. The instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses to active military personnel were identified and predetermined based on the existing POI, the 580ACWW Compendium of Radar-Related Courses 2022 in the 581st Aircraft Control and Training Squadron, 51st Aircraft Control and Warning Group. Also, the extent of practice of the instructional strategies instructors used in teaching radar-related courses was determined through the use of a validated survey questionnaire with data categorization and distributed to the graduates of Radar courses from CY 2022-2024 in Wallace Air Station after seeking permission from the proper authorities and/or officers through a letter request for the conduct of the data gathering procedure. Further, after conducting the survey, the tallying of results was necessary using Excel. After the result was determined, the result was forwarded to the statistician to analyze whether there is a significant difference in the extent of practice of the instructional strategies along the academic and synthetic phases.

The significant difference in the extent of practice of the different instructional strategies was determined through the use of one-way repeated measures Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). ANOVA is an analytic tool used in statistics that splits an observed aggregate variability found within a dataset into two parts: systematic factors and random factors (Kenton, 2024).

The proposed output of the study is a Lesson Exemplar per the instructional strategies mentioned above. This lesson exemplar was formulated or crafted to provide improvement and enhancement in the utilization of each instructional strategy utilized by the instructors teaching radar-related courses at Wallace Air Station. Aiming to provide a better and enhanced teaching-learning process in radar operations.

Ethical Considerations

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The investigation was conducted within the researcher's field of expertise and ensured adherence to the research ethics policy and guidelines of SLC. Before beginning the research, the necessary oral and written consents, permissions, and approvals from significant Military Officials in the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station, and school authorities were obtained.

The research made sure that the participants were aware of the purpose and benefits of the study before they agreed or declined to. Confidentiality was upheld. The researcher ensured that the respondent's privacy was not compromised. The survey instrument was voluntary when it came to writing the respondent's data, such as names, phone numbers, photographs, and videos, which were not included in the paper. The respondents are fully aware that the questionnaires are fully part of the requirements needed to successfully conduct this research.

The researcher diligently avoided plagiarism whenever possible, and proper citations of sources and references were also followed to ensure that the necessary acknowledgement was made and to promote the study's validity. The researcher diligently obeyed and followed the written consent information form for those personnel who would voluntarily withdraw from any part of the research.

Data Analysis

To determine the extent of practice of the instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar courses in Wallace Air Station, a validated survey questionnaire was distributed to all graduates of radar-related courses from CY 2022-2024. After which, the mean was computed from the respondents' scores and was interpreted using the Likert scale based on the 2019 Thesis Manual of SLC.

The Study also employed one-way repeated measures Analysis of Variance to identify the significant differences among the instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses to active military personnel at Wallace Air Station, followed by the Post Hoc Analysis. Confidentiality and anonymity were properly upheld when working with this data. The scale presented below, which was based on the 2019 Thesis Manual of Saint Louis College Inc., was used to assess the extent of practice of the instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar courses in Wallace Air Station.

Table 2
Likert Scale with Interpretation

Scale	Statistical Range	Adjectively Rating	Interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Always Practiced	The adapted strategy has achieved its extended goals and delivered significant results
4	3.51 – 4.50	Often Practiced	The adapted strategy has achieved its specific goals and delivered reliable results
3	2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes Practiced	The adapted strategy has somewhat achieved its goals and delivered adequate results
2	1.51 – 2.50		The adapted strategy has slightly achieved its goals

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		Rarely Practiced	and delivered limited results
1	1.00 – 1.50	Never Practiced	The adapted strategy has not achieved its goals and delivered ineffective results

Results

Extent of Practice of the Instructional Strategies in teaching Radar-Related Courses

The academic phases involved five (5) strategies, namely direct instruction, interactive instruction, experiential learning, collaborative learning, and technology integration, while the synthetic phase also includes five (5) strategies – research or information gathering, practical exercises, assessment, OJT phase (Radar Site On-The-Job), and field study.

Table 3 reflects the results of the one-way repeated measures analysis of variance conducted on the extent of practice of the ten (10) instructional strategies as utilized by instructors of radar-related courses based on two phases: academic and synthetic phases. Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics and reliability indices (Cronbach's alpha) for each instructional strategy domain assessed in the study. Means (M) ranged from 4.32 to 4.75, indicating generally high to very high levels of utilization of instructional strategies by instructors teaching radar courses at Wallace Air Station.

Specifically, the Assessment domain had the highest mean score (M = 4.75, SD = 0.46), followed closely by the Practical Exercises (M = 4.67, SD = 0.44) and OJT Phase domains (M = 4.70, SD = 0.52). In contrast, the Research domain recorded the lowest mean (M = 4.32, SD = 0.72), though still rated as high utilization. Reliability analysis revealed acceptable to excellent internal consistency across the domains, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from .633 (Practical Exercises domain) to .944 (Direct Instruction domain). A repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to determine if statistically significant differences existed among the instructional strategy domains.

Table 3
Exploratory Descriptive, Reliability, and Comparative Analyses Results

Scale	M	SD	DE	Cronbach's a
Direct Instruction Domain	4.46	.47	High	.944
Interactive Instruction Domain	4.48	.48	High	.918
Experiential Learning Domain	4.63	.42	Very High	.767
Collaborative Learning Domain	4.52	.49	Very High	.888
Technology Integration Domain	4.52	.56	Very High	.917
Research Domain	4.32	.72	High	.928
Practical Exercises Domain	4.67	.44	Very High	.633
Assessment Domain	4.75	.46	Very High	.903
OJT Phase Domain	4.70	.52	Very High	.842
Field Study Domain	4.64	.53	Very High	.902
Repeated Measures ANOVA	F (9, 468) = 9.999, p<.001, η ² = .161			

Note. N = 53

Results indicated a significant difference among domains, F(9, 468) = 9.999, p < .001, η² = .161, suggesting that instructors do not utilize all instructional strategies equally. Post-hoc analyses using Bonferroni corrections revealed several significant differences among the instructional domains (see Table 4). Specifically, the Assessment domain was utilized significantly more than Direct Instruction (p

< .001), Interactive Instruction ($p < .001$), Collaborative Learning ($p < .001$), Technology Integration ($p = .002$), and Research domains ($p < .001$). Additionally, Practical Exercises were utilized significantly more than Direct Instruction ($p = .009$), Interactive Instruction ($p = .002$), and Research ($p = .003$). Experiential Learning showed significantly greater utilization than Direct Instruction ($p = .008$) and Research ($p = .010$). Furthermore, OJT Phase was significantly higher compared to Direct Instruction ($p = .018$) and Research domains ($p = .007$), while the Field Study was significantly higher than the Research domain ($p = .009$).

Table 4
Post-Hoc Comparisons via Bonferroni Corrections

Comparison	Mean Diff	SE	T	D	p_{bonf}
Direct Experiential	-0.170	0.042	-4.039	-0.331	.008
Direct Practical	-0.203	0.050	-4.017	-0.395	.009
Direct Assessment	-0.284	0.051	-5.530	-0.554	< .001
Direct OJT	-0.228	0.060	-3.783	-0.443	.018
Interactive Practical	-0.186	0.042	-4.469	-0.363	.002
Interactive Assessment	-0.268	0.050	-5.346	-0.521	< .001
Experiential Research	0.315	0.079	3.975	0.614	.010
Collaborative Assessment	-0.227	0.047	-4.875	-0.443	< .001
Technology Assessment	-0.231	0.052	-4.403	-0.450	.002
Research Practical	-0.348	0.080	-4.344	-0.678	.003
Research Assessment	-0.430	0.082	-5.218	-0.837	< .001
Research OJT	-0.373	0.092	-4.068	-0.727	.007
Research Field Study	-0.323	0.081	-4.015	-0.630	.009

Note. Only the statistically significant findings are reflected in the table

Lesson Plan per Instructional Strategies

Based on the findings, for better and enhanced learning to take place, specifically in utilizing the identified strategies in teaching radar-related courses to active military personnel at Wallace Air Station, a Lesson plan per strategy was crafted as the output of the study. Specifically, a lesson plan for adult learners, particularly military personnel assigned to Wallace Air Station. This serves as a structured guide to facilitate meaningful, goal-oriented learning experiences. There are different purposes, such as providing a clear framework for educators to follow and ensuring lessons are logical and structured. Made sure to address Adult Learning Needs, recognizing their prior experiences, self-directed learning styles, and practical applications. Incorporates real-world relevance, making learning more applicable to professional or personal growth. Defines specific outcomes that learners should achieve by the end of the session. Guides assessment methods to measure learner progress and skill acquisition, which in turn enhances Engagement & Motivation among themselves. Integrates interactive techniques such as discussions, case studies, or problem-solving exercises. Encourages collaborative and experiential learning, fostering deeper understanding, especially in radar operations, which is timely in Wallace Air Station. This lesson plan allows instructors to evaluate effectiveness and make necessary modifications. Encourages reflection and feedback, enhancing future teaching strategies.

Lesson Exemplar per Instructional Strategy Utilized in Military Radar Operations (See Appendix J)

Subjects:

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- 1) Radar Operations and Signal Analysis, 2) Advanced Radar Operations and Tactical Application, 3) Tactical Radar Operations and Real-World Application, 4) Tactical Radar Operations Through Hands-On Experience, 5) Precision Radar Analysis & Tactical Assessment, 6) Team-Based Radar Operations & Tactical Decision-Making, 7) Advanced Radar Operations Using Digital & AI-Driven Systems, 8) Fundamentals of Military Radar Systems & Tactical Applications, 9) Tactical Radar Operations & Signal Interpretation through Interactive Learning, and 10) Tactical Radar Analysis & Intelligence Gathering through Research.

Level: Adult Learners - Military Personnel (Wallace Air Station Operators, Defense Analysts, Tactical Coordinators)

Strategies/Approaches:

Blended Learning (Lecture, Simulation, and Practical Exercises), 2) On-the-Job Training (OJT) (Daily Training Sessions), 3) Field Study (Practical Observations & Exercises), 4) Experiential Learning (Daily Practical Training & Simulated Scenarios), 5) Assessment-Based Learning (Structured Evaluations & Tactical Performance Reviews), 6) Team-Based Radar Operations & Tactical Decision-Making, 7) Technology Integration (Blended Learning Approach with Digital Simulations & AI-Assisted Exercises), 8) Direct Instruction (Lecture-Based, Structured Explanation, Guided Practice), 9) Interactive Instruction, and 10) Research-Based Learning (Data-Driven Learning & Military Case Study Analysis).

Lesson Objectives: By the end of the lessons utilizing the different strategies instructors utilize in teaching radar-related courses, the learners should be able to:

Operate and troubleshoot radar systems effectively in real-world defense applications. 2) Analyze radar signals to distinguish between friendly, unidentified, and adversarial targets. 3) Apply military decision-making protocols based on radar intelligence data. 4) Collaborate within radar teams to improve operational efficiency. 5) Utilize research-based findings to enhance radar system accuracy and effectiveness, and 6) Integrate technology-driven solutions to optimize radar surveillance and threat detection.

These Lesson Exemplars were crafted based on the comments and suggestions of the panel as a means for improvement on the utilization of the strategies at Wallace Air Station, and for the future use of the next researchers to come. The said lesson exemplars utilized approaches that are suited to the particular topic to be discussed in teaching radar-related courses to active military personnel.

Discussion

The findings underscore the high utilization of various instructional strategies in teaching radar-related courses at Wallace Air Station, as perceived by the graduates. A consistently strong application of these strategies demonstrates the program's structured and intentional approach to instructional delivery. The predominance of experiential, assessment-driven, and collaborative strategies reflects a training philosophy rooted in real-world engagement, aligning with the operational needs of military education. Among the most prominent strategies practiced are On-the-Job Training (OJT), Field Study, Assessment, and Experiential Learning. These methods promote applied learning and practical execution, which are essential in preparing military personnel for situational awareness, operational decision-making, and mission-critical tasks. The emphasis on these strategies signifies an understanding of the unique cognitive and performance demands placed on radar operators, surveillance officers, and air battle managers.

The data also points to the frequent and consistent use of Collaborative Learning, Practical Exercises, and Technology Integration, which further enrich the learning experience by fostering teamwork, hands-on engagement, and adaptation to evolving technological environments. These

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strategies reinforce the constructivist learning model and align with adult learning theories that highlight learner autonomy, relevance, and experience-based instruction. Notably, the significant differences observed among strategy implementation levels suggest areas of strength and opportunities for further enhancement. While high-impact strategies are consistently utilized, the relatively lower emphasis on Research/Information Gathering and Direct Instruction indicates a potential to strengthen critical thinking, conceptual understanding, and investigative capabilities. Addressing this could bolster strategic thinking and adaptability in rapidly changing threat environments.

The results align with instructional frameworks such as the ADDIE model (Basu, 2021) and support pedagogical principles like Problem-Based Learning (Niculescu, 2019), which emphasize learner-centered, contextualized, and performance-oriented approaches. These principles are particularly relevant in military contexts, where learners must transfer knowledge to high-stakes, real-time operational settings. Overall, the findings demonstrate a well-implemented instructional strategy that supports military training goals while adhering to best practices in adult education. The output crafted from this study offers practical value, serving as a model for refining instructional practices and informing future curriculum development across similar military training environments. Emphasizing research-based strategies and leveraging interactive, technology-driven tools could further elevate the effectiveness of radar education programs and sustain readiness in complex defense scenarios.

The data presented highlight the exploratory descriptive, reliability, and comparative analyses of various instructional strategy domains utilized in teaching radar-related courses at Wallace Air Station. The mean scores (M) and standard deviations (SD) reflect the instructors' reported high utilization in the Assessment domain, to a comparatively lower but still often practiced in the Research domain. Notably, most domains fall within the "Very High" usage category, including Experiential Learning, Collaborative Learning, Technology Integration, Practical Exercises, On-the-Job Training (OJT) Phase, and Field Study. Reliability coefficients, as measured by Cronbach's alpha, demonstrate acceptable to excellent internal consistency, supporting the reliability of the measurement scales. The repeated measures ANOVA confirms significant differences among these domains, indicating instructors do not employ all instructional strategies equally. This suggests purposeful selection of strategies based on their perceived effectiveness or relevance in the radar instruction context.

When considering these findings in light of the existing literature, it is evident that the high utilization of varied instructional strategies aligns well with principles of instructional design prevalent in military education. As Basu (2021) notes, instructional design in military contexts involves systematic development and delivery of education that adapts to learners' diverse needs and ensures consistent and reliable training outcomes. The Wallace Air Station instructors' balanced use of direct, interactive, experiential, and collaborative strategies reflects this principle. Moreover, the strong emphasis on experiential learning and practical exercises corresponds with international research advocating for problem-based learning (PBL) in military training (Niculescu, 2019). PBL, which promotes engagement through solving real-world problems, is particularly suited for adult learners who benefit from relevant, applicable, and hands-on learning experiences. Similarly, the presence of technology integration as a very highly utilized domain supports Baumgartner and Carr-Chellman's (2024) assertion that modern adult education is increasingly influenced by technological advancements, which facilitate more inclusive and effective learning environments. The relatively lower, though still high, utilization of the Research domain might reflect the practical, mission-focused nature of military training, where immediate operational readiness takes precedence over research-oriented activities.

Explaining the results, the predominance of the Assessment domain suggests instructors place significant emphasis on evaluating learner comprehension and skill mastery, which is critical in high-stakes military training to ensure personnel readiness for real-world radar operations. This finding

underscores the alignment of instructional goals with the objectives of the 580th Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, tasked with maintaining vigilant airspace surveillance and responding to aerial threats. The high reliability scores, particularly in Direct Instruction and Interactive Instruction, reveal that these domains are consistently implemented with fidelity, which is essential in structured military education where clarity and standardization are key. The elevated use of experiential, collaborative, and technology-integrated strategies reflects the military's recognition of adult learners' needs for practical, relevant, and technologically supported learning modalities, reinforcing the literature's emphasis on adapting to adult learning theories and cognitive needs (Fensie, 2023).

Practically, these results imply that a multi-faceted instructional approach, combining traditional methods like Direct Instruction with modern strategies such as Technology Integration and Experiential Learning, optimizes learning outcomes in radar-related courses. This supports the study's objective of identifying effective instructional strategies that produce competent radar operators and air battle managers capable of managing complex, dynamic security challenges. Theoretically, the findings confirm the applicability of instructional design frameworks and adult learning theories in military training settings, emphasizing the importance of adapting teaching methods to adult learners' cognitive, emotional, and experiential characteristics. Future curriculum development should continue to emphasize varied and reliable instructional strategies, focusing particularly on enhancing research engagement, which, although less utilized, can foster critical thinking and continuous improvement in military education programs.

The significant variation in strategy utilization revealed by the ANOVA not only reflects the instructors' strategic prioritization but also highlights the evolving nature of military education that blends tried-and-tested direct teaching with innovative, learner-centered approaches. These insights are invaluable for informing the design of lesson plans tailored to adult military learners at Wallace Air Station, ensuring training remains relevant, effective, and aligned with the overarching mission of air defense and national security.

Limitations and Future Directions

Potential weaknesses, constraints, or shortcomings may affect the validity and reliability of the study's findings. Identifying and acknowledging these limitations is an essential part of the research process, as it demonstrates transparency and allows readers to assess the study's credibility. This study serves as the stepping stone for enhanced learning, validation, assessment of instructional strategies, and constant innovation of the process of crafting the program of instructions, SOPs, and Instructional strategies itself at the 581st Aircraft Control and Training Squadron, 581st Aircraft Control and Warning Wing, Wallace Air Station.

For future directions of this study, Enhancing Lower-Rated Domains is suggested. Research received lower ratings compared to experiential and practical learning methods. Future studies should explore more about integrating research-based insights into hands-on activities to make theoretical knowledge more applicable. Assessing the long-term impact of research training on operational readiness in radar stations. Next, Optimizing Practical Exercises. While Practical Exercises were highly rated, their Cronbach's α indicates lower reliability, suggesting variability in responses. Future directions include standardizing training across radar stations to ensure consistency and evaluating different types of practical exercises to determine which ones contribute most to competency.

Military Technology keeps evolving, since the Philippine Air Force continuously revises and crafts the Flight Plan Strategy Map, which allows the different capabilities of different units in the PAF to keep up with the current global trends. Particularly, at Wallace Air Station, the strategic map contains different advances and future directions of the radars, eventually keeping us up to date and not losing track of the current opportunities and possibilities that could hinder the mission and vision of the Wing, if not

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being monitored properly. Relative to this, for the future direction of the study, Expanding Technology Integration is of utmost importance. With Technology Integration showing strong ratings, future research should explore: Advanced AI-driven radar simulations to improve operator decision-making, and assessing real-time data analysis tools for better threat detection. Also, Refining Direct Instruction Methods is necessary. Direct Instruction was rated high but lower than more interactive methods. Future improvements could include: Blending interactive multimedia elements with traditional direct instruction, and investigating the effectiveness of hybrid instruction models in military training. Further, Assessment scored the highest, indicating strong implementation. Research should: Explore adaptive assessments tailored to individual learning progress, and identify which assessment formats work best in military radar training scenarios.

For the limitations of the study, it was revealed based on the findings that there are Sample Size Constraints that may limit the generalizability of findings to broader military training contexts. Future research should expand sample sizes to include personnel across different ranks and locations. Potential Bias in Self-Reported Measures was also suggested after the results were released. The study relied on subjective responses, which may be influenced by personal biases or training experiences. Future research could incorporate objective performance metrics, such as training success rates and radar detection accuracy. Next, there should be a distinction between Short-Term vs. Long-Term Effects. The current findings may reflect immediate training impacts, but the long-term effectiveness of instructional strategies remains unclear. Future studies should conduct follow-up evaluations to track skill retention and operational efficiency over time. Reliability Variability Across Domains, like Practical Exercises and Experiential Learning, had lower reliability, suggesting inconsistencies in respondent ratings. Standardized evaluation criteria should be developed to improve consistency in future studies. Lastly, it was found that there were Comparative Analysis Constraints. While Repeated Measures ANOVA confirmed significant differences between instructional domains, Bonferroni corrections may have limited the ability to detect nuanced effects. Future research should explore alternative statistical models, such as multivariate analysis, to investigate deeper relationships.

On the conducted post hoc analysis, since it was confirmed on the repeated ANOVA that there is a significant difference in the level of effectiveness of the instructional strategies utilized by the instructors in teaching radar-related courses at Wallace Air Station, future directions and limitations were also included based on the post hoc comparisons. For the future directions of the study, there is a need to improve the effectiveness of the strategy, Direct Instruction, in utilizing it during the teaching of radar-related courses at Wallace Air Station. Direct Instruction showed significantly lower ratings compared to Experiential Learning, Practical Exercises, Assessment, and OJT. With this, future studies should investigate alternative methods to enhance direct instruction in military training. Explore hybrid instructional models, integrating direct instruction with interactive or technology-driven approaches. and assess the impact of scenario-based learning to strengthen theoretical understanding.

Secondly, optimization of practical exercises and Hands-On Training, the teaching of radar courses to active military personnel. Practical Exercises were rated higher than Research, indicating that hands-on training was preferred. Future research should include the Long-term effectiveness of practical exercises on skill retention of the learners attending radar-related courses. How simulation-based training compares to real-world exercises in radar station operations, and the Standardization of practical exercises to improve consistency.

Enhancing Research-Based Instruction was also seen to be included in the future research of the study. Research showed significantly lower ratings when compared to Practical Exercises, Assessment, OJT, and Field Study. Instructors should explore how to make research more applicable to real-time military decision-making. Research plays a vital role in the innovation process, and looking for a

probable solution to certain scenarios in radar operations, aircraft surveillance, and air battle management. Also, look for ways to integrate data-driven research techniques into military training.

There is also a need for Expanding Assessment and Technology Integration. Assessment received the highest ratings, demonstrating strong implementation when compared to Research. For future research, there is a need to explore adaptive assessments tailored to military learning environments, which is timely at Wallace Air Station. Evaluate how AI-driven assessments can improve competency tracking in radar training, and investigate the real-time feedback mechanisms in radar operations to enhance learning outcomes.

Further Investigation into Collaborative and Interactive Learning needs to take place for the future directions of the study. Collaborative Learning and Interactive Instruction showed lower ratings compared to Assessment. Future advances should develop group-based problem-solving strategies specific to radar station teams. Explore the role of interactive simulations in improving teamwork and coordination in radar defense systems, and examine how peer mentoring programs influence skill development.

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